

On the Application of Redundant Manipulator Techniques to the Control of Platoons of Autonomous Vehicles

Bradley E. Bishop

Daniel J. Stilwell

Systems Engineering
United States Naval Academy
118 Maryland Avenue
Annapolis, MD 21402

bishop@usna.edu

stilwell@usna.edu

Abstract— In this paper, we discuss the parallelism between redundant manipulator control and the control of platoon-level functions for systems of autonomous vehicles. We cast the platoon formation problem in an analogous manner to traditional redundancy resolution, and discuss techniques for control of the platoon.

I. INTRODUCTION

Control for platoons of cooperating robotic vehicles has been extensively studied under both the systems-theoretic and behavior-based paradigms (e.g., [1], [2], [3]). These approaches have tended to focus on either rigidly defined and constrained platoon element functions (such as cooperative material handling or specific formation regulation), or on generic platoon “behaviors.” In the former case, the platoons may possibly require a great deal of communication and sophisticated planning and/or control algorithms. In the behavior-based case, provability of system performance is often unachievable (see, e.g., [1]). In [4], the author uses system-theoretic techniques to prove the performance of a hunting behavior, effectively fusing the two approaches in an intuitive way.

In this work, we present a new formulation of the platooning problem that offers flexibility for behavioral integration while simultaneously relying on well-established system-theoretic robot control methods. Specifically, we will use redundant manipulator control techniques to address the problem of platoon control and formation synthesis.

Several approaches to multiple-robot systems have used techniques based on redundancy resolution (see e.g., [3], [5] and references therein). These methods have typically relied on the rigid connections that exist either implicitly (in that the system consists of multiple manipulators rigidly connected, as in a walking robot) or explicitly (in that the robots are all grasping and manipulating a common, rigid object). In this work, we focus on systems of mobile robots that do not possess rigid kinematic relationships. We demonstrate how tasks can be synthesized using redun-

dant manipulator techniques, and discuss the implications for platoon formation and navigation. Additional related work on formation synthesis can be found in [6], [7] (for decentralized methods utilizing graph theory and *a priori* leader path plans) and [8] (for dynamic programming methods), as well as their associated references.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section II, we offer a synopsis of standard techniques for redundant systems, and define our problem in this framework. In Section III, we develop the control suite for our system. Section IV includes simulated examples demonstrating the nature and performance of our sample architecture. Section V offers conclusions, implications and future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

Given a system with states q_1, \dots, q_n , a function $f(q) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ has a Jacobian matrix $J(q)$ given by:

$$J(q) = \frac{\partial f(q)}{\partial q} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{f}(q) = J(q)\dot{q}$.

In the case of robot manipulators, q is the vector of joint variables and $f(q)$ the forward kinematic equations describing the end-effector location. Systems where $n > m$ are called *redundant* manipulators, as the number of task variables (end-effector coordinates) are less than the number of available degrees of freedom. Basics of redundant manipulator control can be found in [9].

A typical approach to the control of redundant manipulators is to project secondary tasks, such as criterion optimizations, onto the null space of the Jacobian. Thereby, the redundant degrees of freedom of the manipulator are utilized while simultaneously carrying out some primary task(s) (such as regulation of the platoon center and distribution of the vehicles about that center).

In the case of a platoon of r autonomous vehicles, we can choose a state vector q given by the concatenation of the individual units' positions (in 2D here, for simplicity) with the x components at the top and the y at the bottom of the vector. We can then choose as our primary objective

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any task that can be written as a differentiable function of the platoon state q . In this paper, we will choose platoon mean (average position) and variance as the two primary task functions. Other possible tasks include matching a geometric function by forcing the error residual of the platoon elements to zero, forcing a desired value of the principle angle of the platoon, etc. Note that, in these cases, the actual positions of the platoon elements are not dictated: some flexibility remains in exact positioning after these functionals are achieved.

For our case, we define the primary task variables as the platoon-level mean and variance in each coordinate, as given by:

$$f(q) = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_x \\ \sigma_x^2 \\ \mu_y \\ \sigma_y^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r q_i \\ \frac{1}{r-2} \sum_{i=1}^{2r} (q_i - \mu_x)^2 \\ \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=r+1}^{2r} q_i \\ \frac{1}{r-2} \sum_{i=r+1}^{2r} (q_i - \mu_y)^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

From this task vector, we can generate a Jacobian matrix and a null space projection. For simplicity, we assume that each unit is both holonomic and velocity-controlled, so that $\dot{q} = q^d$. We note that while most robotic vehicles are not holonomic, several instances of viable holonomic systems exist. Further, we note that if the generated motion of the platoon is considered as *relative* velocity, as is common in applications where there is an underlying drift velocity at all times, local holonomicity is guaranteed when linearizing about a trajectory [10].

Under the assumptions above, the Jacobian matrix for the system is given by the following:

$$J(q) = \begin{bmatrix} J_x & 0 \\ 0 & J_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$J_x(q) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{r} & \cdots & \frac{1}{r} \\ \frac{2}{r-2}(q_1 - \mu_x) & \cdots & \frac{2}{r-2}(q_r - \mu_x) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

and where J_y is defined equivalently. We note that $J(q)$ is singular only in the case where $q_1 = \cdots = q_r$ or $q_{r+1} = \cdots = q_{2r}$. We will assume that such a degenerate case is not encountered, for sake of simplicity, although our controller could easily be modified to take such a situation into account [11].

Given this formulation of the platoon control problem, we now wish to consider selection of additional platoon tasks and the control techniques that would be appropriate in each case.

III. CONTROL OF PLATOONS OF AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES USING REDUNDANCY

Typical tasks for platoons of autonomous vehicles include formation tracking [2], hunting and encirclement [4], material transport [5], etc. Using our formulation of the platooning problem, we will be able to synthesize a variety of tasks using redundancy-based controllers. Recognizing that the mean and variance of the platoon in each coordinate dictate the platoon location and allowable spread, we

must now cast desirable tasks such that they can be projected onto the null space of the Jacobian for these functions (as we would for *any* arbitrary primary task functions). First, let us define a set of suitable control architectures.

Formulation of control techniques for redundant manipulators has received a great deal of study. The two traditional techniques that we will consider are task prioritization [12] and the gradient descent technique [9].

Task prioritization is a method by which a secondary task is projected onto the null space of the primary task Jacobian. The secondary task is written in identical terms to the primary task, using a secondary Jacobian matrix. Given a secondary task based on a system function $f_2(q)$ and associated Jacobian $J_2(q)$, the task prioritization controller can be given by:

$$E = K(f(q)^d - f(q)) + \dot{f}(q)^d \quad (5)$$

$$E_2 = K_2(f_2(q)^d - f_2(q)) + \dot{f}_2(q)^d \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{q} = J^\dagger E + \tilde{J}_2^\dagger (E_2 - J_2 J^\dagger E) + (I - J^\dagger J)(I - \tilde{J}_2^\dagger \tilde{J}_2)v \quad (7)$$

where $f(q)^d$ and $f_2(q)^d$ are the desired task variables, K and K_2 are control gains, J^\dagger is the Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse given by $J^T(JJ^T)^{-1}$, $(I - J^\dagger J)$ is the projection operator onto the null space of the Jacobian, and $\tilde{J}_2 = J_2(I - J^\dagger J)$. The task defined by E_2 is guaranteed to be carried out only when it does not interfere with the task defined by E . Further, the effect of the primary task on the secondary task is taken into account through the $J_2 J^\dagger E$ term, allowing better tuning and performance of the secondary task controller than if such a term were not present. The v term is an arbitrary velocity vector that is projected onto the null space of both J and J_2 (if such a space exists).

Unlike the task prioritization method, gradient projection does not rely on the generation of an explicit Jacobian and desired task value. Rather, this approach uses the projection of a task gradient onto a Jacobian null space. The standard velocity-based gradient projection controller is given by:

$$\dot{q}^d = J^\dagger (K(f(q)^d - f(q)) + \dot{f}(q)^d) + (I - J^\dagger J)v \quad (8)$$

Any global measure $h(q)$ can be locally optimized through the projection of its gradient onto the null space of a Jacobian (either the primary or the combination of the primary and secondary) by letting v in (7) or (8) be given by $K_{opt} \partial h(q) / \partial q$, where K_{opt} is a gain.

Given these two approaches to redundant manipulator control, we will now define a set of tasks and associated controller terms for our platooning problem.

A. Obstacle Avoidance

For a platoon of autonomous vehicles to successfully navigate an unstructured environment, it is necessary for the vehicles to be able to avoid obstacles. We assume that each unit is capable of measuring the location of adjacent obstacles and units, and we rely on an artificial potential

field technique [13] for maintaining some desired standoff distance from those objects.

The task prioritization approach has been used for obstacle avoidance, although in rigidly constrained cases ([12], [14]). In our case, using multiple mobile robots, such techniques are difficult to apply. We *will* use a combination of task prioritization and gradient projection for our control laws; however, for obstacle avoidance, we will rely on a classical technique using gradient projection.

A straightforward method for on-line path planning in mobile robotics is the use of artificial potential field (APF) techniques. In these approaches, the robot is “attracted” to a desired goal and “repulsed” from obstacles (and other robots) as if it were a charged particle. In our case, we are interested only in the repulsive forces, which we will use to attempt to maintain some minimum standoff distance from every other object in the operational area.

We begin by thinking of a repulsive “force” F , from a nearby object, acting on the robot. The object should repel the robot with increasing force as the robot approaches. Since we are working in a velocity (rather than acceleration) space, we will write the “force” vector as a velocity command (standard in mobile robotics). Since we do not have a known desired unit trajectory, we will not attempt to use a Jacobian-based task prioritization method. Instead, we will project a velocity term onto the null space of the primary Jacobian. This velocity term (pointing always away from the obstacle in task space) should approach infinity (in magnitude) as the obstacle and vehicle connect, and should drop off as the vehicle moves away from the obstacle. Thus, the projected velocity term is essentially a projected gradient, maximizing the distance between the obstacle and the vehicle over the null space of the primary task. For finite desired platoon variances, there is a hard limit on the distance between any given unit and the center of mass of the platoon. Hence this null space projection is guaranteed to be stable if the primary task controller is stable (see [9] for some analysis techniques for projected gradient and task prioritization methods).

Let d_i be the distance between unit i and an obstacle. Then, for obstacle avoidance, we take v in (8) to be

$$V_{obst}(j) = \begin{cases} \begin{cases} \frac{\eta}{d_j} \cos \theta_{obst} & \text{for } d_j < \rho \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} & \text{for } j \in \{1, \dots, r\} \\ \begin{cases} \frac{\eta}{d_j} \sin \theta_{obst} & \text{for } d_j < \rho \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where θ_{obst} is the heading from the nearest obstacle point, ρ is the maximum distance at which an object has an effect on the robot, and η is a gain.

We are interested in avoiding not only obstacles but also other robots. We therefore include a second APF term that pushes vehicles apart, using exactly the form of V_{obst} , but replacing obstacles with other vehicles. This new term, V_{veh} , has a unique ρ and η . For purposes of simplicity, we use V_{obst} to denote the summation of all APF terms.

B. Task Synthesis

Given that we have a platoon that obeys the redundancy assumption for our primary set of tasks (i.e., more than two units), we have the freedom to select secondary tasks so long as they are compatible with the primary task and do not deleteriously affect the performance of the obstacle avoidance routine. Note that we can choose secondary tasks that locally conflict with the obstacle avoidance routine without fear of collision, since the obstacle avoidance gradient reaches infinity at a collision point. Thus, to guarantee obstacle avoidance (where possible), we simply have to guarantee that all secondary task vectors are bounded.

In the following subsections, we will consider tasks that might be accomplished by a platoon of autonomous vehicles. Our focus will be primarily on optimizing the behavior of a single unit from the platoon, a fundamentally different approach than previous work in this area.

B.1 Reconfigurability

In redundant manipulator control, a common secondary objective is maximization of *manipulability*, given by $\sqrt{JJ^T}$. In essence, this optimization task has the goal of minimizing the joint velocities required for a desired end-effector velocity. Manipulability is, therefore, a measure of the ease of reconfiguration of the end-effector at a given pose [15].

In our platoon analog to the redundant manipulator, a similar idea arises, although with a fundamentally different form. For autonomous vehicles, each unit must obey some velocity limit, determined by the limited actuation and viscous friction. This velocity limitation can have a profound impact on the reconfiguration of the platoon. To emphasize the nature of this problem, consider the effect of projecting a desired velocity for unit 1, $v_1 = (1, 1)$, onto the null space of the Jacobian (i.e., while simultaneously maintaining the desired primary task functional values, such as mean and variance of the platoon). In the case of three units, this is equivalent to considering

$$V_1 = (I - J^\dagger J) [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0]^T. \quad (10)$$

If the magnitude of $V_1(1)$ is larger than that of $V_1(2)$ and $V_1(3)$, and the magnitude of $V_1(4)$ is larger than that of $V_1(5)$ and $V_1(6)$, then we are guaranteed that unit 1 can locally use its full available velocity, up to saturation, in any direction without saturating the velocity of any other unit. Our goal, then, is to optimize the ability of a given unit to reconfigure, essentially forcing the projection of a desired velocity (for that unit) onto the null space to be larger for the unit in question than for any other unit. If this is the case, we can guarantee maximal use of resources in a local manner. In simplest terms, we want to minimize the impact of a specific vehicle’s reconfiguration on the rest of the platoon, which is functionally constrained by the primary tasks.

This task is well-suited to the gradient projection method. Given unit i whose reconfigurability is to be op-

timized, we use the following

$$V = (I - J^\dagger J)v_d \quad (11)$$

where $v_d \in \mathbb{R}^{2r}$ with

$$v_d(j) = \begin{cases} 0 & \forall j \notin \{i, i+r\} \\ 1 & \text{when } j \in \{i, i+r\} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

We wish to maximize $V(i)$ and $V(i+r)$. The gradient term for the optimization is then

$$V_{opt} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial V(i)}{\partial q^x} \\ \frac{\partial V(i+r)}{\partial q^y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where $q = [q^x, q^y]^T$ and we are essentially concatenating two distinct optimizations due to the decoupled nature of the Jacobian for the primary task vectors that we have selected (otherwise we would have additional terms).

Although we exclude sample calculations for brevity, we note that this gradient is only unbounded as the unit approaches infinity (which cannot occur if the desired variance is bounded). Thus, the reconfigurability optimization task is compliant with the primary control and obstacle avoidance.

Our method for optimizing reconfigurability is based on the principle of null-space shaping that is inherent in manipulability optimization, but allows for more sophisticated and directed shaping of the Jacobian null space. Our technique has implications in standard redundant manipulation, especially for robots with velocity and/or acceleration (torque) limits.

We now turn our attention to another secondary task that makes reconfigurability a reasonable choice for a task in autonomous vehicle control.

B.2 Heading Control

One goal of controlling reconfigurability is to perform an intercept maneuver with a specific unit. In this situation, we would be interested in not only optimizing the reconfigurability of a unit but in maintaining a desired relative heading from the center of the platoon to the unit in question (assuming an incoming target).

We do not wish to cast the problem such that a desired position of the unit is given with respect to the platoon mean: this would be tantamount to reducing the redundancy of the system by one unit. Instead, we can guarantee that the unit approximately achieves a given heading, but specify no distance along this heading. Obstacle avoidance and optimization should determine the radius of the location, retaining one degree of redundancy.

To perform heading control, we cast the location of unit i in polar coordinates with an origin at μ_x^d and μ_y^d , the desired center of mass of the platoon. The desired heading is θ^d , so the error vector for heading only is $\theta^d - \theta_i$. We write a Jacobian for this task as follows:

$$u = (y_i - \mu_y^d)/(x_i - \mu_x^d) \quad (14)$$

$$\theta_i = \text{atan}(u) \quad (15)$$

$$J_2 = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial q} \quad (16)$$

We note that the j^{th} element of J_2 will be zero unless $j \in \{i, i+r\}$. Using this J_2 and an error term $E_2 = K_2(\theta^d - \theta_i)$ (assuming that $\dot{\theta}^d = 0$), we can use the control method of (7) to regulate heading. We note that this term is ill-defined when the vehicle in question is located at the platoon mean, which can easily be avoided by using a repulsion function (i.e., making the center of mass an obstacle for the vehicle performing heading control).

IV. SIMULATION EXAMPLES

In this section, we will demonstrate the basic principles of our approach to platoon control using a simple example. Our control (\dot{q}) will consist of four terms:

1. A primary Jacobian pseudoinverse control term given by (8):

$$\kappa_1 = J^\dagger E = J^\dagger K(f(q)^d - f(q)) + \dot{f}(q)^d \quad (17)$$

2. A gradient projection obstacle avoidance term (see section III-A) given by:

$$\kappa_2 = (I - J^\dagger J)V_{obst} \quad (18)$$

3. A task-priority-based heading control term (see section III-B.2) for unit i given by:

$$\kappa_3 = \tilde{J}_2^\dagger (K_2(\theta^d - \theta_i) - J_2 J^\dagger E) \quad (19)$$

4. A null space optimization term (see section III-B.1) for unit i :

$$\kappa_4 = K_{opt}(I - J^\dagger J)(I - \tilde{J}_2^\dagger \tilde{J}_2)V_{opt} \quad (20)$$

So that the entire control system is given by:

$$\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + \kappa_3 + \kappa_4 \quad (21)$$

We place an obstacle (e.g., a mothership, captive or diver) at location $x = 3$, $y = 1$, with a radius of 0.25. The platoon is ordered to fixate on the obstacle (so that $\mu_x^d = 3$ and $\mu_y^d = 1$) with variance of 0.5 in each coordinate. We choose $K = 3$ for this example.

We select $\rho = 3$ and $\eta = 1$, with equivalent values for inter-unit repulsion given by $\rho = 1$ and $\eta = 0.1$. We assume that each unit has a maximal dimension of 0.1 and operates in a two dimensional configuration space (no rotation is considered). An initial simulation with no optimization or heading control (i.e., $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2$) is shown in Figures 1 – 3. Notice that unit 2 avoided the obstacle as it attempted to pass through to achieve the desired mean and variance. The effect of the APF on the entire platoon can be seen in the qualitative change in motions of each unit as the vehicles approach the obstacle. Figure 3 shows the value of V (from (11)) for unit 1.

We now add the optimization control term with $K_{opt} = 3$, maximizing local reconfigurability in both axes for unit 1, and neglecting the effects of heading control (i.e., we let $\tilde{J}_2^\dagger \tilde{J}_2 = 0$ in κ_4). The control is $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + \kappa_4$. The results are shown in Figures 4 and 5. We see significant improvement in the reconfigurability of unit 1 along the x -axis while maintaining the fortuitous high reconfigurability along the y -axis seen in the previous example. This

Fig. 1. Unit motions with $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2$

Fig. 2. Errors in primary tasks for $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2$

indicates that unit 1 is able to maximally affect a repositioning maneuver without being limited by the saturation of velocity on any of the other units. The errors in primary variables are identical for every simulation, as the primary task is unaffected by our additional control terms.

Figures 6 and 7 show the results of simulations involving the full system (21). Here, we let $\theta^d = \pi/4$ with $K_2 = 1$. We see, in this simulation, that the optimization is carried out simultaneously with the heading control. No vehicles collide with one another or with the obstacle. We do note, however, the effect of the APF term on the steady-state error of the heading system, as seen in Figure 8 when $\theta_d = -\pi/8$ (we exclude the unit motions for brevity).

Interestingly, as we increase K_{opt} , the steady-state error for heading control increases, due to the increase of the effect of a velocity forcing term on unit 1. Increasing the reconfigurability of a specific unit also increases the effects of potential field forces on that unit, resulting in greater steady-state error on secondary tasks due to obstacle and intra-unit repulsion. At the cost of maximal null space obstacle avoidance ability, we could project the APF term onto the null space of both J and J_y and eliminate the steady-state error.

Fig. 3. Reconfigurability values for unit 1, $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2$

Fig. 4. Unit motions with $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + \kappa_4$

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work we have presented a new formulation of the platoon control problem, relying on fundamental similarities between platoon formation synthesis and redundant manipulator control. The benefits of the proposed approach are that no explicit path planning is required, no formation specification (e.g., specific relative positions of the elements in the platoon) is necessary, and a great deal of flexibility is inherent in the structure. The primary contribution of this work is the fundamental re-casting of the platooning problem and its impact on formation control. Future work in this area involves appropriate primary and secondary task definitions for a variety of operational situations.

Additional open issues in redundant-manipulator-analog control of platoons involve questions of decentralization and communication. Our previous work on decentralized control and the associated communication burden for platoons of cooperating vehicles will form the basis for our investigations [10].

We note that our control structure is designed such that it is possible for collisions to occur when the obstacle avoidance is incompatible with the primary task (e.g., when

Fig. 5. Optimization criteria for $\dot{q} = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + \kappa_4$

Fig. 7. Optimization criteria and error, $\theta_d = \frac{\pi}{4}$, full control

Fig. 6. Unit motions with full control (21) and $\theta_d = \frac{\pi}{4}$

Fig. 8. Optimization criteria and error, $\theta_d = -\pi/8$, full control

the obstacle is too large). In these cases, switching control may be a suitable alternative. We note that methods for redundant manipulator control have been successfully applied under provable logic-based switching schemes [11], demonstrating that such controllers lend themselves to variable architectures such as those implicit in behavior-based methods. Thus, casting the platooning problem in this framework allows a designer to use tools from both the system-theoretic and behavior-based approaches to platooning.

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